

REGULATORY HARMONIZATION FOR FINTECH AND DIGITAL BANKING: BALANCING INNOVATION AND CONSUMER PROTECTION

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ABSTRACT

Digital transformation in the financial services sector has triggered rapid innovation through the rise of fintech and digital banking, offering faster, more efficient, and more inclusive financial services. However, such acceleration also presents legal issues related to consumer protection, data security, transparency, and financial system stability. These conditions require regulatory harmonization to balance innovation with legal certainty and public protection. This study employs a normative legal research method and comparative analysis of regulatory frameworks in Indonesia, Singapore, and the European Union. The findings indicate that mechanisms such as regulatory sandbox, risk-based supervision, and proportionate regulation are essential to achieve regulatory harmonization. This research proposes policy recommendations to strengthen consumer protection without hindering innovation, including integrated data governance standards, enhanced digital financial literacy, and improved regulatory coordination mechanisms.

Keywords: Consumer Protection, Digital Banking, Fintech, Regulatory Harmonization, Supervision.